

THEORETICAL ANALYSIS OF THE PHENOMENON OF INDEPENDENT THINKING AND THE CONCEPT OF CREATIVE THINKING IN HIGHER EDUCATION STUDENTS

Yakubova Barno Baxtiyorovna

Senior Lecturer of the "Department of Languages and
Humanities",

Andijan State Technical Institute

b.yakubova 1990@gmail.com,+99877-037-00-57

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Abstract. This article provides information about the importance of demonstrating the level of independent thinking in students and the advantages of using research methods and indicators that reflect the characteristics of this process. The article discusses the concept of independent thinking, its role and significance in shaping the personality, the opinions of psychologists and educators from various perspectives and scales based on their goals. It also addresses the formation of students' worldview and thinking through educational activities, the role of independent thinking in ensuring the intellectual and spiritual development of the younger generation, their conscious attitude towards the social system, the process of independent creative work, and the tasks that systematize the goals of education in pedagogical activities. The article explores the correct formation of students' independent thinking abilities, the need for consistent reinforcement of skills, as well as the importance of rationally organizing and effectively managing students' independent learning.

Key words: Independent thinking, students, personality model, education, psychology, methodology, innovation, pedagogy, development, critical thinking.

In today's world, numerous urgent studies emphasize the importance of providing proper education and upbringing to ensure a person's full development and health. This includes the full realization of intellectual and creative potentials such as creativity, competence, logical thinking, reflection, abilities, talents, and skills. It also involves the formation of healthy character traits, the development of noble and sound ideas and ideologies, enabling individuals to follow their own path without losing direction. Such education helps ensure that a person can appropriately serve the development of their nation, people, society, and state.

In the current context of rapid scientific and technological development worldwide, special attention is paid to the development of learners' creativity, logical thinking, and pragmatism at all levels of continuous education, including the efficiency and quality of higher education.

Internationally, educational reforms are being implemented that focus on fostering creative and logical thinking, self-awareness, self-study, self-development, and the manifestation of creativity among students. These reforms are based on the introduction of modern education systems centered around these influential factors in the learning process. [2.80]

Creative concepts and approaches have contributed to the development of human civilization and culture across various regions of the world, stimulating the advancement of natural sciences, philosophy, art, and humanities. It is known that creative thinking differs sharply from coincidental ideas. It is considered a genuine competence based on knowledge

and experience, enabling people to achieve expected results in sharp and complex situations. At the same time, the global community views innovation ideas and creative thinking as general initiatives, focusing on overcoming emerging complexities by mastering innovative ideas, knowledge, and skills.

Analyzing various views on a person's creative activity, it can be emphasized that its manifestation is closely related to the psychological state in many respects. The state of any system can be described by certain indicators that reflect the degree of interaction between the system's specific characteristics and its environment or society. When studying the dependence of a subject's activity on their internal states, it is recommended to consider the subject as a holistic physiological and psychological system interacting with its environment and society.

Based on the analysis of sources, it is clear that the development of a person's independent thinking is linked to the direct advancement of intuition. Intuition is considered the foundation of creative thinking activity and assists in finding solutions to creative problems.

From the historical analysis of views on human creative activity, it is known that ancient Greek philosophers (Aristotle, Democritus, Plato, Thales, and others) regarded creativity and intuition as inner insight and the highest capacity of reason. Foundational ideas in the study of intuition were put forth by B.Spinoza, R.Descartes, I.Kant, V.F.Asmus, and A.Bergson. The problem of intuition was deeply embedded in the philosophical theory of knowledge and was typically interpreted as a dichotomy between two types of cognition: intuitive, direct, unproven knowledge and rational, mediated knowledge supported by evidence.

The issue of creativity is increasingly attracting wide attention from psychologists both in our country and abroad. Creativity is the sum of an individual's creative abilities, characterized by unusual ideas, a departure from traditional thinking systems, and the capacity to quickly solve problematic situations. The readiness to develop new ideas is considered an independent factor in the structure of this ability. According to A.Maslow, creativity is "an innate creative orientation common to everyone, which is often lost under the influence of the environment." [5.40]

What compels a person to enhance and demonstrate their independent thinking? If we clarify this issue, it becomes necessary to identify ways to nurture and develop a creative person.

There are several views on the role of motivation in the formation of an individual's creative activity; we will analyze some of them.

Thus, the internal motives of human creative activity include the following:

1. Utilizing the innate human need for exploration. Every living being, especially humans, actively studies the environment they find themselves in from the first days of life and tries to adapt to it. The natural need for exploration (curiosity) compels individuals to analyze situations, draw conclusions, and make creative decisions.
2. The instinct for preservation, reproduction, and survival. In extreme conditions, there is an increase in creative actions and efforts aimed at preserving life and continuing the species. History provides many examples of this.
3. Meeting basic material needs (food, shelter, clothing, etc.). A large portion of the global patent fund consists of creative decisions aimed precisely at satisfying these human needs. [6.32]

4. Meeting basic spiritual and social needs (self-respect, recognition, love, self-expression, self-development). When basic material needs are met, spiritual needs based on the desire to understand one's place and significance in life emerge. A person begins to acknowledge and value themselves, develops a sense of self-respect, and then expects respect from close ones and eventually from everyone. This never-ending and constantly growing need is one of the strong motives behind the manifestation of creativity.

5. Self-interest, striving for power, and charisma. For some, the desire to become wealthy and powerful is a strong motivation for developing their creative abilities. This is likely related to satisfying the need for personal security and survival. [7.58]

6. Laziness, self-preservation, parasitism. In many cases, idleness and the desire to exploit the environment are considered among the motivating forces of human development, especially in its early stages. Primitive humans, tired of searching for food, began to engage in agriculture, avoided hunting, invented traps, did not want to walk — invented the horse-cart, train, automobile, etc. [8.84]

When we think about education, we can distinguish the following main components in the creative activity of learners: [9.145]

- ❖ The need, interest, and inclinations for creative activity
- ❖ A transformative attitude toward the subjects and objects being studied
- ❖ Readiness for the process of restructuring
- ❖ Heuristic potential
- ❖ The activity of restructuring itself

The essence of creative educational activity should be viewed as an integral characteristic of the individual, where needs, interests, and the purposeful unity of the activity are manifested in its individualized reflective-restructuring activity at the highest level. Based on the above, the creative development of a person is directly the sum of the development of qualities, complex forms of psychological processes, the discovery of novelty, assimilation of the unknown, acquisition of new knowledge, formation of interests and needs, development of creative abilities, independence, and initiative. [10.60]

References:

1. Erkayev A. Criteria of Freedom of Thinking. – 2006. – No. 2. p. 12-19.
2. Karimova V., Sunnatova R. Methodological Guide on Organizing Independent Thinking Exercises. – Tashkent: Sharq, 2000. – 193 pages.
3. Musaev J.P. Technology for Modeling Educational Materials Directed at Independent Thinking. – "School and Life" journal, 2008, issues 7-8, pp. 1-12.
4. Nishonova Z. Psychological Foundations for the Development of Independent Creative Thinking: Abstract of Doctoral Dissertation in Psychology. – Tashkent, 2005. – 38 pages.
5. Nishonova Z. Independent Creative Thinking and Personality Traits. – Tashkent: "People's Education", 2001, No. 4, pp. 38-42.
6. G'oziev E., Ikromov J. The Influence of Independent Thinking on Perfection // J. People's Education. – 2001. – No. 4. Pp. 31-37.
7. Yakubova B.B. "Creativeness and creativeness in a person the need for the development of adjectives." // Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development-2022. – pp. 56-59
8. Smolkin AM Methods of active learning. - M.: Higher school, 1991. - P. 84.

9. Baxtiyorovna Y.B. FORMATION OF INDEPENDENT THINKING AMONG YOUNG PEOPLE-TODAY IS THE MOST RELEVANT DAY IN PEDAGOGY AS A FUNCTION //Proceedings of International Conference on Modern Science and Scientific Studies. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 3. – S. 143-148.

10. Bakhtiyarovna Y.B. Independent work of students through the internet pedagogical conditions of organization //Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development. – 2022. – T. 3. – S. 59-61.

